

Development And Evaluation Of Metronidazole Benzoate Loaded Lipomeric Nanoparticles (LPHNP's) For The Treatment Of Colon Bacterial Infection

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ABSTRACT

The colon is a critical site for bacterial infections, including conditions like colitis, enteritis, and pseudomembranous colitis often caused by anaerobic and facultative bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Clostridioides difficile* and *Escherichia coli*. Conventional oral delivery of antimicrobials like Metronidazole benzoate is often limited by premature drug release, systemic side effects, and reduced efficacy at the infection site. Metronidazole benzoate (MET) is a novel potent and broad spectrum nitroimidazole group of antibiotics effective against both Gram- positive and negative aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. The present study formulates a lipid polymeric hybrid nanoparticles for antibacterial Metronidazole benzoate (MET) agent with Stearic acid (lipid), Chitosan (polymer) and Pluronic F127 to improve controlled release of the drug by single-emulsion-solvent evaporation technique. Optimization was performed via 3² Factorial design with mean particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) of optimized MET loaded LPHNPs (F1-F9) were measured in the range of 299- 368 nm and 0.215-0.269, respectively. The drug encapsulation efficiency (EE%) and loading capacity of MET loaded LPHNPs were measured in the range of 64.9-80.4% and 3.8-27.45%, respectively. Nanoparticles produced was capable of achieving 24-h controlled release in vitro on gastric and intestinal environments. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values of the MET loaded LPHNPs (F5) appeared typically to be four fold lower than those of Metronidazole benzoate in the case of Gram -negative strains and was 2-4fold more potent than those of Metronidazole benzoate against Gram positive strains of bacteria. These results concluded that the newly optimized MET loaded LPHNPs were more potent against Gram-positive strains of bacteria as compared to Gram-negative bacteria. Research studies suggest the promising use of MET-LPHNPs as an effective therapeutic agent for Colon Bacterial Infection.

Keywords: Metronidazole benzoate, LIPOMER, 3² Factorial design, drug release, antibacterial activity, Colon Bacterial Infection

INTRODUCTION

About Colon Bacterial Infection

The human colon is a complex ecosystem inhabited by a diverse array of microorganism, playing a crucial role in maintaining health and preventing disease. However, disruptions to this delicate balance can lead to colon bacterial infections, which are a significant public health concern. These infections can cause a range of symptoms, from mild diarrhoea to life-threatening complications¹. Colon bacterial infections are a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), diarrheal diseases are

responsible for estimated 1.6 million deaths annually, with a significant proportion attributed to bacterial infection. Colon bacterial infections occur when pathogens, such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Clostridioides difficile*, *Salmonella*, and *Shigella*, adhere to and invade the colonic mucosa, leading to inflammation and tissue damage. The gut microbiome plays a critical role in maintaining homeostasis, and disruptions to this balance can increase susceptibility to infection. This Colonic bacterial infection may leads to serious life-threatening diseases like infectious colitis, Inflammatory bowel disease, Cancer, etc².

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

About Colon.**Fig 1. Anatomy of the Colon**

The colon is the major part of the large intestine, extending from the cecum to the rectum. It is approximately 1.5 meters (5 feet) long and is divided into five main parts:

- 1) Caecum
- 2) Ascending colon
- 3) Descending colon
- 4) Transverse colon
- 5) Sigmoid colon

1) Caecum

Pouch-like beginning of the colon.

Receives chyme from the small intestine via the ileocecal valve.

Attached to the appendix.

2) Ascending Colon

It is about 8 inches long.

Begins at superior border of caecum .

Function – It carries faeces from the caecum .

3) Descending Colon

Less than 12 inches.

Function- Store the remains of digested food that will be emptied into the rectum.

4) Transverse Colon

It is about 18 inches long .

Function – Bacteria further breaks down the food , process called fermentation.

5) Sigmoid Colon

It is S shaped segment.

About 18 inches long which lies posterior to urinary bladder.

Function – Stores faecal waste until they are ready to leave the body.

About Antibacterial Drug

Metronidazole benzoate (MET) is a broad -spectrum antibiotic used to combat anaerobic bacteria and some parasites. It is a nitro- imidazole derived from the reduction of the nitro group on the molecule by the bacteria and thus determines the emergence of toxic metabolites. These compounds used their bactericidal action with molecular DNA destruction, stopping the DNA repair process. Metronidazole is a drug that penetrates bacteria through the mechanism of passive diffusion, and is activated in the cytoplasm where it is transformed into free nitrogen radical. Having cytotoxic activity, it inhibits synthesis and damages

DNA, stopping the multiplication of bacteria. Furthermore, the DNA breakage caused by metronidazole metabolites leads to bacterial cell damage³.

About Lipid Polymer Hybrid Nanoparticles (LPHNPs)

In recent times, the advent of nanotechnology has emerged in successfully overcoming the pitfalls of the conventional delivery systems. Nanotechnology has proved to be a powerful ally to researchers in combating a plethora of disorders and overcoming several biological barriers. Nanotechnology in the field of nanomedicine represents various nanocarriers ranging between 1 and 1000 nm. Nanocarriers have attracted tremendous attention of researchers in

delivering various drugs, oligonucleotides, proteins, genes, etc. to the targeted site. Nanocarriers offer various features in drug delivery which include solubility, permeability and bioavailability enhancement, alteration in pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic profile of incorporated drug, protection from metabolizing enzymes and harsh gastro-intestinal conditions, stability in biological matrices, prolonged drug release, reduction in adverse effects, etc.

DRUG & EXPIENTS PROFILE

Drug Profile

Metronidazole benzoate

Table1.Physicochemical Properties of API14

	Metronidazole benzoate
Properties	Details
Description	Whitish Cream -Coloured Crystalline powder
Chemical Structure	
Molecular Formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄
IUPAC Name	2-(2-methyl-5-nitro-1H-imidazol-1-yl) ethyl benzoate
Solubility	Metronidazole benzoate is practically insoluble in water. It is freely soluble in dichloromethane, soluble in acetone, slightly soluble in ethanol, and very slightly soluble in ether.
Log P	-0.27
BCS Class	IV
Melting Point	99-102°C
Molecular weight	275.26 g/mol
Drug Class	Broad Spectrum Antibiotic
Dose	Oral Metronidazole benzoate Suspension 200 mg/5 mL
pKa	3.27
Protein Binding	10-20%
Adverse effects	Nausea, Mouth dryness, Epigastric pain, Gastrointestinal intolerance, Hypersensitivity Reactions

Pharmacokinetic/Pharmacodynamic Properties of API

Properties	Details
Therapeutic Class	Antiamoebic, Antiparasitic , Antibacterial
Metabolism	Metronidazole benzoate is a prodrug that undergoes rapid hydrolysis in the body to release the active drug metronidazole and benzoic acid. This hydrolysis is catalyzed by esterases, primarily in the liver and plasma. The released metronidazole is then metabolized in the liver through oxidation and conjugation. The main metabolic products are 2-hydroxymethyl metronidazole and metronidazole acetic acid, which are further conjugated with glucuronic acid. These metabolites, along with a small amount of unchanged metronidazole, are primarily excreted in the urine
Half life	8hours
Elimination	The drug and its metabolites are eliminated mainly via the kidneys, with approximately 60–80% excreted in the urine about 20% of that as unchanged metronidazole. A smaller portion, around 6–15%, is excreted in the feces. The elimination half-life of metronidazole in healthy adults is approximately 8 hours.
Mechanism of action	Metronidazole works by entering anaerobic microorganisms and being chemically reduced by intracellular electron transport proteins. This reduction converts its nitro group into reactive intermediates that bind to DNA, causing strand breaks and inhibiting nucleic acid synthesis. As a result, the affected cells cannot replicate, leading to cell death.

EXCIPIENTS PROFILE

Physicochemical Properties of Chitosan¹⁵

Chitosan

Chemical Name	β -(1→4)-linked D-glucosamine (deacetylated unit) and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine(acetylated unit).
Synonym	Chitosan, Poliglusam
Molecular Weight	Between 10,000 and 1,000,000
Chemical Structure	
Physical and Chemical Properties	It is odorless, white or creamy-white powder or flakes. Acidity/Alkalinity: pH= 4.0-6.0(1%w/vaqueous solution) Density: 1.35-1.40g/cm ³ Glass Transition Temperature:203 ⁰ C
Functional Category	Chelating agent, Stabilizing agent and Reducing agent

Applications	Chitosan is used in Pharmaceutical formulations for drug delivery applications such as controlled drug delivery applications. It also used in pharmaceutical forms including microspheres, tablets, Nanoparticles, gels and films.
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Stearic Acid**Properties of Stearic acid¹⁵**

Chemical Name	Octadecanoic acid
Molecular Formula	$C_{18}H_{36}O_2$
Molecular Weight	284.484g/mol
Chemical Structure	
Melting Point	57.23 ⁰ C
Physical and Chemical Properties	In its solid form, it appears as a white solid And has mild pungent, oily odour. Density: 0.9408 g/cm ³
Solubility	Soluble in alcohols, phenyls, and alkyl acetates, Carbon tetrachloride, carbon disulfide, methyl formate and DCM
Functional Category	Lubricating agent, Food additives, Coating agent
Uses	Used as lipid in Lipomer Nanoparticles
Applications	It is used as a lubricating agent. It is used as a food additive. Used in the production of detergents. It is used in cosmetics, soaps, shampoos, etc.

Pluronic F127**Properties of Pluronic F127¹⁵**

Chemical Name	2-[2-(2-hydroxyethoxy)propoxy]ethanol
Synonyms	Poloxamer407, Therabloat
Molecular Formula	$C_7H_{16}O_4$
Molecular Weight	164.20g/mol
Chemical Structure	
Melting Point	52-57 ⁰ C
Physical and Chemical Properties	White crystal, Non-ionic Surfactant; pH- 5-7; HLB- 22
Functional Category	Surfactant, Stabilizing agent, Emulsifier
Uses	Emulsifier in Lipomer Nanoparticles
Applications	It is used in Pharmaceutical for Stabilizing formulation. Usually inert substances added to a prescription in order to provide suitable consistency to the dosage form. These include binders, matrix, base or diluent in pills, tablets, creams, salves, etc.

MATERIALS AND INSTRUMENT**Chemicals and their Supplier**

The Preformulation and formulation study was carried out by using different chemical and API. The list of chemical and material with their supplier are as following.

List of Drug and Excipients

Sr.No.	Chemical	Supplier
1.	Metronidazole benzoate	Sunpras Healthcare Pvt. Ltd
2.	Stearic Acid	Loba Chemi Pvt. Ltd
3.	PluronicF127	Merck Pvt. Ltd
4.	Chitosan	Loba Chemi Pvt. Ltd
5.	Ethyl acetate	Loba Chemi Pvt. Ltd
6.	Acetic Acid	Loba Chemi Pvt. Ltd

Instruments and their manufacturers

Metronidazole benzoate. The list of instruments use with their manufacturer given in the following table.

The Preformulation and formulation study was carried out by using different chemical and API i.e.

List of Equipment and their Manufacturer

Equipment	Company	Model
Digital Weighing Balance	Shimadzu	AUX220
FTIR	Bruker	ALPHA-T
U.V.Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu	1900+
Probe Sonicator	Sonics	VCX130
Digital Ultrasonicator	Labman	LMUC3
Hot air oven	Lab Hosp	230
Remi-cooling Centrifuge	Remi Elektrotechnik	CM-12PLUS
Particle size analyzer	Horiba	SZ-100V2
SEM	CIQTEK	3200
Lyophilizer	BioEra	Clout
Environment Test Chamber	LAB Hosp	CS-03
DSC	Thermal Analysis System , Hitachi	DSC7020

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Appearance

Characterization of API

Table12.Description of Metronidazole benzoate

Description	Standard	Observed
Colour	Whitish cream -coloured powder	Whitish cream – coloured powder
Odourless	Odourless	Odourless
Taste	Bitter	Bitter

MELTING POINT

The melting point of the drug matched with the values found in literature indicating the purity of sample.

Table 13. Practical and Standard Melting point of MET

Drug	Melting Point	
	Observed	Standard
Metronidazole benzoate	98-102°C	97-102 °C

Determination of Absorption Maxima (λ max)

The absorbance of pure Metronidazole benzoate drug were measured at 313 nm (λ max) in Methanol, at 268 nm (λ max) in 0.1N HCL (pH 1.2), at 319 nm (λ max)

in (pH 6.8) and at 318 nm (λ max) in PBS (PH 7.4) . Standard curve was plotted between concentration of drug on x axis v/s absorbance on y-axis to get the linearity and regression equation.

F Absorption maxima of MET in Methanol at 313 nm (λ max)**Calibration curve of MET in Methanol**

Conc. (μ g/ml)	Abs (λ max)
2	0.274
4	0.403
6	0.527
8	0.65
10	0.781

Calibration curve of MET in 0.1 N HCL (pH 1.2)

Conc.(µg/ml)	Abs. (λ max)
2	0.147
4	0.280
6	0.411
8	0.562
10	0.697

Calibration curve of MET in PBS (pH 6.8)

Absorption maxima of MET in PBS (pH 7.4)

Absorption maxima of MET in PBS (pH 7.4)

Calibration curve in PBS (pH 7.4)

Calibration curve of MET in PBS (pH 7.4)

Conc.(µg/ml)	Abs(λ max)
2	0.262
4	0.407
6	0.539
8	0.694
10	0.826

FT-IR Determination of drug

FTIR Spectrum of Metronidazole benzoate

Reported and Standard frequencies of MET

Peak assignment	Standard Frequency(cm^{-1})	Observed Frequency(cm^{-1})
N=O Stretching	1350-1390	1359
C-H Stretching	2800-3100	2832
C=O Stretching	1200-1300	1260
O-H Bending	3200-3500	3411
C=C	1400-1600	1471

Conclusion: The IR spectrum of pure Metronidazole benzoate was recorded by FT-IR spectrometer as shown which was compared with standard functional group frequencies. The major peak of corresponding functional group were observed.

Discussion - The thermal behavior of Metronidazole benzoate determined by DSC. DSC analysis of Metronidazole benzoate showed endothermic peaks at $103^{\circ}C$, which are concerned with the melting of drug.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Drug-Excipient compatibility study

The drug-polymer mixture was taken and observed after 14 days, at $40^{\circ}C \pm 2^{\circ}C/75\% \pm 5\%RH$ results shown in table 19. During the 14 day period no any caking, discoloration, gas formation, liquefaction in mixture in the vials. The FT-IR Spectrum of drug, drug- excipient mixture were compared to find any changes in frequency of functional group with respect to functional group of drug. Metronidazole benzoate appeared in spectra with out any remarkable change in their position. FT-IR of drugs-excipient, prior to before and after compatibility study.

DSC curve of Metronidazole benzoate

Compatibility Study of Drug and Excipi

Physical Mixture	Colour Change	Cake Formation	Liquification
Metronidazole benzoate	No	No	No
MET +Stearic acid	No	No	No
MET+Chitosan	No	No	No
MET + Pluronic F127	No	No	No
Physical mixture of all	No	No	No

Before

After

FT-IR Spectra of Metronidazole benzoate before and after Compatibility study

Before

After

FT-IR Spectra of mixture of Metronidazole benzoate + Stearic acid before and after compatibility study

Before

After

FT-IR Spectra of mixture of Metronidazole benzoate + Chitosan before and after compatibility study

FT-IR Spectra of mixture of Metronidazole benzoate + Pluronic F127 before and after compatibility study

FT-IR Spectra of mixture of all ingredients

Conclusion – From the above infrared spectroscopic study it was concluded that there was no any changes observed in the graph obtained before and after the compatibility study. Hence it can be concluded that the selected excipient used in the formulation are compatible with drug.

Formulation batch of Metronidazole benzoate loaded Lipid Polymer Hybrid Nanoparticles(LPHNP)

Formulation batches of lipomers

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Response 1	Response 2
Batches	A: Stearic acid Conc. (mg)	B: Pluronic F127 Conc.(mg)	Particle size (nm)	Entrapment efficiency (%)
F1	200	25	292	62.5
F2	400	25	308.4	75.94
F3	600	25	332	64.53
F4	200	50	330.2	70.79
F5	400	50	315.8	72.48
F6	600	50	360	80.72
F7	200	75	302.5	68.53

F8	400	75	316.6	85.54
F9	600	75	328	76.28

Optimized Formulation

ANOVA results for responses

The analysis of variance is essential to test significance and adequacy of the model. Fisher's F-test value which is the ratio between the mean square of the model and the residual error, performs these comparisons. A model, were significant, with very small p-values ($p < 0.05$). The other term coefficients were not significant ($p > 0.05$).

The "Lack of Fit Test" compares the residual error to the pure error from replicated design points. The lack of fit F-value of is not significant as the p-value is > 0.05 . The non-significance lack of fit showed that the model was valid for the present work.

Response 1: Particle size

Particle size ANOVA for linear model

Source	Sum of Squares	dF	Mean squares	F value	P value
Model	3069.67	5	613.93	15.32	0.0240 Significant
A: Stearic Acid	1021.81	1	1021.81	25.50	0.0150
B: Pluronic F127	167.48	1	167.48	4.18	0.1335
Lack of Fit	120.22	3	40.07		

Response 2: Entrapment efficiency: Entrapment efficiency ANOVA for linear model

Source	Sum of Squares	dF	Mean squares	F value	P value
Model	588.82	5	117.76	23.62	0.0129 Significant
A:Stearic Acid	127.51	1	127.51	25.57	0.0149
B:Pluronic F127	62.92	1	62.92	12.62	0.0380
Lack of Fit	14.96	3	4.99		

In vitro drug release study of LPHNP formulation

Discussion: A biphasic release pattern was observed from MET-loaded L-P-NPs. In the first phase, a burst release of the drug was observed at 4 h (44.15%), probably due to the surface-adsorbed drug and easy diffusion of the media into the nanoparticles. A sustained release of the drug was observed after 4 h of the study until 24 h in the second phase; it may be due to the lipid and polymer of the NPs, and subsequent immobilization may contribute to the slow release of the drug. The sustained release of the drug ultimately enhanced the bioavailability and, hence, reduced the dose and dosing frequency.

Ex -vivo drug release study

Ex vivo study of formulation was performed in 0.1 N HCL (pH 1.2), PBS (pH6.8) and PBS (pH7.4) to know the pattern and mechanism of Metronidazole benzoate from lipid polymer hybrid nanoparticles.

Ex -vivo drug release study data

Time (Hrs)	%CDR of MET	% CDR of F5
0	0	0
1	0.000	0.000
2	0.000	0.000
3	0.417	0.622
4	2.994	3.201
5	5.085	6.838
6	7.455	10.257
7	8.853	12.578
8	10.810	17.600
9	11.858	20.881

Ex vivo drug release study of LPHNP formulation

SEM Analysis

The morphological visualization of Metronidazole benzoate loaded lipomeric nanoparticles for providing information about lipomers surface was carried out by using SEM. Obtained SEM image showed that Metronidazole benzoate loaded lipomers has porous, spherical shape and surface characteristics. Figure shows the SEM image of optimized lipomers formulation at 25 – fold magnification.

SEM image of optimized MET LPHNPs

Conclusion: The morphological characteristics of the MET loaded lipomeric nanoparticles were examined using SEM. The SEM image of lipomers reveals that the nanoparticles were spherical with solid dense structure.

DSC Analysis

The thermal behavior of the physical mixture was determined by DSC. DSC analysis of MET loaded lipomeric nanoparticles showed endothermic peaks at 57.4 °C mV, indicating a phase transition in the material. The heat flow value of -57.7 mV provides insight into the amount of heat absorbed during this transition.

DSC image of optimized MET -LPHNP

Antibacterial Activity

The antibacterial activity of MET-LPHNPs and Metronidazole benzoate was performed on gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria to identify the efficacy.

Escherichia coli and *Staphylococcus aureus* were bacteria's used in study. Disc diffusion method was employed to evaluate the antibacterial efficiency.

Antibacterial activity of MET -LPHNP and MET on *Escherichia coli*

Antibacterial activity of MET- LPHNP and MET on *Staphylococcus aureus*

Discussion: The zone inhibition measured for Standard and Formulation in above figures. The zone diameter are found to be 9.47mm, 11mm, 8.1mm & 13mm respectively. The biggest zone inhibition were showed in formulation for *S.aureus*. The antibacterial activity of prepared LPHNPs were compared with Metronidazole benzoate (0.1%) using selected species of microorganism such as *Escherichia coli* and *S.sureus*. It observed that formulation F5 showed greater activity on *S.aureus* as compared to *E coli*.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present study was undertaken to formulate and evaluate nanoparticles of a broad spectrum antibiotic Metronidazole benzoate. Preformulation studies were carried out initially and based on that, different batches were formulated with different concentrations of pluronic F127 as surfactants, stearic acid as lipid with using chitosan as polymer by emulsification solvent evaporation method .As a result of these studies, it is possible to conclude that the Metronidazole benzoate- loaded Lipomer formulations, particularly the F5 formulation, demonstrated improved release behaviour, which would aid in reducing dose frequency and minimizing side effects. In this investigation, Metronidazole benzoate loaded LPHNPs were formulated and optimized with the intention to enhance their bioavailability and antibacterial activity. The results revealed that the MET loaded lipomers exhibited a mean particle size of 315.8 nm. The high entrapment efficiency 90.18 % and zeta potential. An in vitro drug release study showed a biphasic release pattern of the optimized formulation of MET LPHNPs. The formulation shows minimum zone of inhibition in Gram-ve as compared to Gram+ve. Hence, it is concluded that Metronidazole benzoate loaded LPHNPs promise a better therapeutic efficacy and could be a choice of replacement for the conventional formulation, with benefits of low dose requirements and better patient compliance

REFERENCES

1. Madni A, Tahir N, Rehman M, Raza A, Mahmood MA, Khan MI, et al. Hybrid Nano-carriers for Potential Drug Delivery. Advanced Technology for Delivering Therapeutics. InTech; 2017.
2. Cai J, Huang H, Song W, Hu H, Chen J, Zhang L, et al. Preparation and evaluation of lipid polymer nanoparticles for eradicating *H. pylori* biofilm and impairing antibacterial resistance In vitro. Int J Pharm. 2015;495 (2):728–37.
3. Bou S, Wang X, Anton N, Bouchaala R, Klymchenko AS, Collot M. Lipid-core/polymer-shell hybrid nanoparticles: synthesis and characterization by fluorescence labeling and electrophoresis. Soft Matter. 2020;16(17):4173–81.

4. Cun D, Jensen DK, Maltesen MJ, Bunker M, Whiteside P, Scurr D, et al. High loading efficiency and sustained release of siRNA encapsulated in PLGA nanoparticles: quality by design optimization and characterization. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2011;77(1):26–35.
5. Tawfik MA, Tadros MI, Mohamed MI. Lipomers (Lipid- polymer Hybrid Particles) of Vardenafil Hydrochloride: a promising dual platform for modifying the drug release rate and enhancing its oral bioavailability. *AAPS PharmSci Tech.* 2018;19 (8):3650–60.
6. Lee SM, O' Halloran TV, Nguyen ST. Polymer-caged nanobins for synergistic cisplatin–doxorubicin combination chemotherapy. *J Am Chem Soc.* 2010;132 (48):17130–8.
7. Bhardwaj A, Mehta S, Yadav S, Singh SK, Grobler A, Goyal AK, Mehta A. Pulmonary delivery of antitubercular drugs using spray-dried lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles. *Artif Cells Nanomed Biotechnol.* 2016 Sep;44(6):1544-55.
8. Bachhav SS, Dighe VD, Kotak D, Devarajan PV. Rifampicin Lipid-Polymer hybrid nano particles (LIPOMER) for enhanced Peyer's patch uptake. *Int J Pharm.* 2017 Oct 30;532(1):612- 622.
9. Garg N. K., Tyagi R. K., Sharma G., Jain A., Singh B., Jain S., et al., Functionalized Lipid-Polymer Hybrid Nanoparticles Mediated Codelivery of Methotrexate and Aceclofenac: A Synergistic Effect in Breast Cancer with Improved Pharmacokinetics Attributes. *Mol. Pharm.* 2017, 14(6), 1883–1897.
10. Guo P, Buttar BA, Xue HY, Tran NT, Wong HL. Lipid- polymer hybrid nanoparticles carrying linezolid improve treatment of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) harbored inside bone cells and biofilms. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2020 Jun;151:189-198.

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